

THE EFFECTS OF INSTITUTIONAL ENVIRONMENT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AT HIGHER LEVEL OF LEARNING: A CASE STUDY OF PUNJAB UNIVERSITY LAHORE

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ABSTRACT

The present paper is an empirical research-oriented attempt that finds out the effects of institutional environment on the academic performance of the students of University of the Punjab, Lahore. Institutional environment is the set of formal laws, rules and regulations, teaching methodology, institutional norms, values, customs and behavior. Institutional environment is play vital role in student academic performance. A Quantitative research methodology was adopted for this study. Simple random sampling technique was used. Total sample size was 180. Interview schedule was used as the tool for data collection. The data were processed by using SPSS. This study found that 45.0% students' reward/encouragement on the part of teachers, (43.9%) conducting sufficient internal exams, (45.0%) university library and (36.7%) problem solving. Role of institutional head positively affected the academic performance of the students as found 45.0% were fulfilling their academic goals and targets that was revealed by 37.8% their successful past results.

Keywords: Institutional Environment, Academic Performance, Administration

JEL Codes: B15, I20

I. INTRODUCTION

Institutional environment is the set of formal laws, rules and regulations, teaching methodology, institutional norms, values, customs and behavior. The institutional environment is providing to access the information about formal and informal learning activity. Institutional environment plays vital role in student academic performance. Institutional environment is a widely discussed topic in research from many years. Different issues in institutions are gaining the attention of institutions, teachers and policy makers. Element of student performance can help teachers to modify teaching methods and institute to give out their resources for that reason. It helps out to the policy makers for the planning and implement strategies to improve the effectiveness of education, as education plays vital role in grow of individual efficiency as well as economic growth.

Better educational environment influences on students' academic performance in better manner and adverse educational environment affects students' academic performance in negative manner. The study also suggested that school should try to maintain the institutional services and student, teacher interaction should be high. Teachers should motivate all students (Chukwuemeka, 2013). Cooperative Institutional Research Program found that there are numerous factors that impact understudy accomplishment but motivation and institutional environment are two most important among others (Turner & Bowen, 1999). Higher Education Administration accentuates the imperative part of confirmation of determination as an approach to comprehend scholarly accomplishment, measured by the normal level point (McGrath & Braunstein, 1997; Tross et al., 2000; Braxton, 2000).

Institutional environment plays a positive role in students' academic performance and improvement in academic achievement (Wenglinisky, 2001). Institutional environment has manipulated the students learning, students grooming, important role in society, emotional and ethical development. School environment engages the students in positive activities, which are helpful for students. From the support of school environment students become

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supportive, caring, responsible, honest and well-mannered and students avoid the use of bad language, violence and solve the behavioral problems. This research emphasizes the positive role of school because that thing is helpful in survival in society. School environment is supportive in student character building, respectful relationship with peers and adults at school and out of school. Which students have good experiences in school life become more motivated, active and engage our self in learning process? Those students are in touch with teachers and participate in different activities (Eric, 2005).

Another study explored that though the institutional environment and scholastic execution is of much importance yet the location of the institution is another important factor for students motivation and for increasing their affiliation feelings with institution (Arul & Vimala, 2012; Onukwo, 2004). The study describes the factors of institutional environment. Location of institution is one of the factors that affected students' academic performance. Sometime educational institutions are located near by the noisy area or sited in the center of a city where goings-on disturb the education of the students. Student academic performance depends on institutional environment, if institutions fulfill the needs like institution's placement, school place of piece and school climate (Barry, 2005). Significance of this study was based on teaching skill, climate, financial status and student performance (Hoy, Kottkamp & Rafferty, 2003). Ideal institutional environment is included understudy security physical space, scholastic environment and understudy medical problems underpin physical wellbeing (Barry, 2005).

There is a critical relationship between the physical environment of the institution and scholarly accomplishment. This is more noteworthy in terms of Physical administrations, human ownership and their interrelationship. On the other hand poor administration, absence of space, the format of the seats in the classroom, absence/improper library and research facility negatively impacts on the learning environment for students (Sunday, 2012; Benware & Deci, 1984). Lizzio, Wilson & Simons (2002) found that the institutional environment and administrations majorly affect understudy results. For instance, Darling-Hammond & Snyder (2001) contend that lessening class size could enhance learning, while availability of suitable research apparatuses and instructional materials could altogether enhance understudy accomplishment. In addition, Devadoss & Foltz (1996) found that the physical environment with elements more solace, security, better acknowledgment obviously can be great as far as enhanced learning and results. They accentuated that nature of social connection adds to and upgrades the innovative capacities of understudies. As indicated by them, an intuitive situation where understudies have the flexibility to pick obligations, bolster for wonderful thoughts shaped to gain from slip-ups and urged to raise a commitment to basic leadership aptitudes and achievement.

Peer and institutional atmosphere strongly influence the student educational outcome. Educational institutions are considered second home and plays vital role in student educational life. Teacher(s) and headmaster are available there for learner help motivates the students for hard work, gives tasks, encourage the learners (Denial & Felix, 2014). Teachers are assumed an essential part in the improvement of training and understudy accomplishment (Engin-Dermir, 2009). Butit was indicated fundamental issues of nature of instructors and state of mind, non-responsibility of understudies aimed their reviews. They invest a little energy in the learning environment (Duruji, Azuh, & Oviasogie, 2014). As indicated the role of physical and staff assets assumed as influential in students outcomes/result producing (Abbasi & Mir, 2012). For instance, professional instruction can enhance understudy accomplishment. Enhancing the nature of training is a marker of enhanced understudy accomplishment (Prosser and Waterhouse, 1999). The quality and energy invested by the educators, understudies' scholarly outcomes and strategies for instructing approaches enhance comprehension of the ideas/concepts of the instructor (Heinesen, 2010). The study of Engin Demir (2009) proposed the need to utilize suitable exhibition of techniques, administrations and fundamental electronic segments of instructors to encourage learning.

The requirement for exhaustive educating and learning approach meets the diverse levels of University Bedürfnisse. Locating to cooperation's between staff, understudies and institutional foundations greatly affect the students' academic performance. Moreover, organizations ought to prepare to enhance systems that can encourage learning in their surroundings (Gainen, 1995). The tragic picture of educational institutions in Pakistan expressed as inadequate found in the study of Hussain (2012) and these negative/poor outcomes in quality education are general aftereffects of foundations that extends to Cracked dividers and floors in class, Missing toilets, Lack of workplaces and seats, Unfulfilled transport, Lack of sufficient security framework, Lack of drinking water supply, Lack of power, Lack of games fields, Teacher deficiency, Lack of satisfactory classrooms, Overloaded classes, Lack of new instructive innovation, Lack of emergency treatment gear and so forth. The private institutions of corporate sector are also creating problematic situations for the students and parents economically, psychologically and socially. Status queue

and other sub-divisions among students are also the product of present education systems in society. Moreover socioeconomic status also matter a lot (Romer, 1993; Durden& Ellis, 1995; Newman-portage, Lloyd & Thomas, 2009; Haider and Ali, 2015; Ali, 2015; Ali, 2018; Ali and Bibi, 2017; Sajid and Ali, 2018; Kassem et al., 2019; Senturk and Ali, 2021; Roussel et al., 2021).The core objectives of the present research paper were to assess the effects of institutional environment on the academic performance of the students of University of the Punjab, Lahore and to find out the relationship between Institutional Environment and Academic Performance of the university students.

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A cross sectional Quantitative Research design was adopted for the current study. Geographical universe of the study was the Institute of Social and Cultural Studies (ISCS), University of the Punjab, Lahore. The ISCS was consisted on six departments having 1800 students in BS and Master Degree Classes. The research team took 10% sample which was 180 students through simple random sampling. Interview Schedule was used as the tool of data collection. 20 interviews (10 from male and 10 from female) were conducted in pre-testing phase. Collected data were processed through SPSS.

III. CONCEPTUALIZATION

The conceptualization of the variables employed in the present study is addressed in the following with details for better understanding of the readers.

IV. INSTITUTIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Institutional environment is characterized by the elaboration of rules and requirements which individual organization must conform in order to receive legitimacy and support (Scott, 2002). Institutional environment is included to provide the buildings, furniture, equipment, instructional materials, the teachers, the peer group and other people, who are involve the development of students (Gagne, 1997).Institutional environment fulfills all the requirements of students like well-educated teachers who motivate the students and satisfy them in question answer session this will create the interest of students in lecture(s), teaching methodology helps to clarify concepts of students and creates the friendly environment in class. Institutes make available University Library for students’ readings, research and other such academic activities and provide peaceful institutional environment.

V. ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Academic performance mean outcome of educational targets and/or goals. Students set the short or long term goals during education and then achieve the goals. Academic achievement means completing the degree from school, college or university (Bossaert et al., 2011).Past academic performance is paying the inner satisfaction and encourages the students for hard work in present degree. Students discuss the concepts during exams preparation and show the positive attitude in exams.

VI. VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Institutional Environment was the independent variable whereas Academic Performance was the dependent variable.

VII. INDICATORS OF VARIABLES OF THE STUDY

Sr. no.	Variables	Indicators
1	Institutional Environment (independent variable)	Rules and regulations, Security System, High Educated teacher, Interesting lectures', Calm and peaceful environment, Methodology of teaching, University Library, Ignored, Friendly environment in class, Satisfaction
2	Academic Performance (dependent variable)	Goals and targets, satisfied, encourage to work hard, academic Performance, discussing academic work/revising for examination, skills to be organized, finishing home task, parents satisfied, passing exams, positive attitude

Index (scale)

Institutional Environment

SD = Strongly Disagree

D = Disagree

N = Neutral

A = Agree

SA = Strongly Agree

Academic Performance

SD = Strongly Disagree

D = Disagree

N = Neutral

A = Agree

SA = Strongly Agree

VII. DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE DATA

Descriptive statistics is the term given to the analysis of data that helps describe, show or summarize data in a meaningful way (Statistics Laerd, 2016). Descriptive statistics therefore enables us to present the data in a more meaningful way, which allows simpler interpretation of the data. From measures of central tendency, frequency distribution method was used for describing the central position of collected data for the present study.

Table 1: Demographic Statistics

Demographics		f	%
Age group	age(17-19)	35	19.4
	age(20-22)	103	57.2
	age(23-25)	42	23.3
Gender	Male	72	40.0
	Female	108	60.0
Area	Rural	87	48.3
	Urban	93	51.7
Schooling	English Medium	124	68.9
	Urdu Medium	56	31.1
Educational Program	B.S	71	39.4
	M.A	109	60.6
Family System	Joint	94	52.2
	Nuclear	86	47.8

The above table is about the demographic profile of the respondents of the study. As per the age of the respondents, more than half (57.2%) of the respondents were from the age (20-22) years old whereas less than one fourth (23.3%) were from age (23-25) and (19.4%) were from age (17-19). As per the gender of the respondents, exact three fifths (60.0%) of them were females whereas (40%) were males. As per the area of the respondents, more than half (51.7%) of them were from urban areas whereas less than half (48.3%) were from rural areas. As per schooling of the respondents, more than two third (68.9%) of them were from English Medium Schools whereas less than one third (31.1%) were from Urdu Medium Schools. As per the current educational program of the respondents, little

more than three fifth (60.6%) of the respondents were from MA whereas more than one third (39.4%) were from BS Program. As per the family system, more than one half (52.2%) were from joint family system whereas less than half (47.8%) were from Nuclear family system.

VII.I. INSTITUTIONAL ENVIRONMENT

Table 2: Institutional Environment

		SD	DA	N	A	SA	TOTAL
Teachers give extra work/assignment to enhance understanding in subjects they teach	f	16	20	37	70	37	180
	%	37	11.1	20.6	38.9	20.6	100.00
Teachers reward/encourage me when I perform well in class	f	12	12	25	81	50	180
	%	6.7	6.7	13.9	45.0	27.8	100.00
We usually have sufficient internal Exams	f	11	13	56	79	21	180
	%	6.1	7.2	31.1	43.9	11.7	100.00
I am free to consult teachers after class in case I do not understand a concept	f	13	23	38	66	40	180
	%	7.2	12.8	21.1	36.7	22.2	100.00
I am free to consult the Head teacher at any time in case of any problem	f	17	27	42	66	28	180
	%	9.4	15.0	23.3	36.7	15.6	100.00
We have sufficient time in university for preparation of the exams	f	18	24	43	54	41	180
	%	10.0	13.3	23.9	30.0	22.8	100.00
Environment is helpful for study in our classrooms	f	18	22	28	69	43	180
	%	10.0	12.2	15.6	38.3	23.9	100.00
Teachers mark and return assignments on time	f	13	24	38	64	41	180
	%	7.2	13.3	21.1	35.6	22.8	100.00
Our University has a motto, vision and a Mission that are clearly understood and followed by students	f	16	19	50	60	35	180
	%	8.9	10.6	27.8	33.3	19.4	100.00
Our university library has adequate with relevant books relating study/subject requirements for students	f	11	16	22	81	50	180
	%	6.1	8.9	12.2	45.0	27.8	100.00

The above table showed that more than one third (38.9%) of the respondents were agree that extra work/assignment given by teachers enhance understanding of the students whereas 8.9% students were strongly disagreeing, 11.1% disagree, 20.6% neutral, and 20.6% strongly agree in this regard. This table showed that less than one half (45.0%) of the respondents were agree that teachers rewarded/encouraged them when they perform well in class whereas 6.7% strongly disagree, 6.7% disagree, 13.9% neutral, and 27.8% strongly agree. According to the above table, more than two fifths (43.9%) of the respondents were agree that they usually have sufficient internal exams whereas 6.1% are students strongly disagree, 7.2% disagree, 31.1% neutral and 11.7% strongly agree. This table found out that more than one third (36.7%) were agree that they had free access to consult their teachers for understanding concepts even after class whereas 7.2% strongly disagree, 12.8% disagree, 21.1% neutral, and 22.2% strongly agree. This above table showed that more than one third (36.7%) of the respondents were agree that they had free access to Head Teacher for consultation in case of any problem whereas 9.4% strongly disagree students, 15.0% disagree, 23.3% neutral, 15.6% strongly agree. According to this table less than one third (30.0%) of the respondents were agree that they had sufficient time in university for preparation of the exams whereas less than one fourth (23.9%) of them were neutral in this regard. 10.0% students are strongly disagreeing, 13.3% disagree and 22.8% strongly agree. This table showed that more than one third (38.3%) of the respondents were agree that institutional environment is helpful for study in their classrooms whereas 10.0% strongly disagree, 12.2% disagree, 15.6% neutral and 23.9% strongly agree. The above table showed that more than one third (35.6%) of the respondents were agree that their teachers mark and return their assignments on time whereas less than one fourth (21.1%) were neutral, 7.2% students were strongly disagreeing, 13.3% disagree and 22.8% strongly agree. As per the above table it was found that little more than one third (33.3%) of the respondents were agree that students clearly understood and followed the motto, vision and mission of the university whereas less than one third (27.8%) were neutral in this regard. 8.9% students were strongly disagreeing, 10.6% disagree and 19.4% strongly agree. According to this table, less than one half (45.0%) of the respondents were agree that their university library has adequate with relevant books relating study/subject requirements for students whereas 6.1% students are strongly disagreeing, 8.9% disagree, 12.2% neutral, and 27.8% strongly agree.

VII.II. ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

Table 3: Academic Performance

		SD	DA	N	A	SA	TOTAL
I'm fulfilling my academic goals and targets	<i>f</i>	9	15	34	81	41	180
	%	5.0	8.3	18.9	45.0	22.8	100.00
I'm satisfied from my academic performance	<i>f</i>	3	28	37	75	37	180
	%	1.7	15.6	20.6	41.7	20.6	100.00
My past results encourage me to work hard	<i>f</i>	5	12	32	68	63	180
	%	2.8	6.7	17.8	37.8	35.0	100.00
My academic Performance depends on my effort	<i>f</i>	4	8	25	76	67	180
	%	2.2	4.4	13.9	42.2	37.2	100.00
I spend most of my time in university with friends and teachers to discussing academic work/revising for examination	<i>f</i>	10	20	59	54	37	180
	%	5.6	11.1	32.8	30.0	20.6	100.00
My academic performance depends on my skills to be organized	<i>f</i>	3	10	41	72	54	180
	%	1.7	5.6	22.8	40.0	30.0	100.00
I succeed in finishing the entire home task every day?	<i>f</i>	8	21	59	58	34	180
	%	4.4	11.7	32.8	32.2	18.9	100.00
My parents satisfied with my grades/results?	<i>f</i>	6	7	27	84	56	180
	%	3.3	3.9	15.0	46.7	31.1	100.00
I always succeed in passing exams?	<i>f</i>	2	9	26	71	72	180
	%	1.1	5.0	14.4	39.4	40.0	100.00
My positive attitude helps me in exams	<i>f</i>	5	3	21	69	82	180
	%	2.8	1.7	11.7	38.3	45.6	100.00

As per the above table, 5.0% students were strongly disagree, 8.3% disagree, 18.9% neutral, 45.0% agree and 22.8% strongly agree regarding fulfillment of their academic goals and targets. According to this table, 1.7% students were strongly disagree, 15.6% disagree, 20.6% neutral, 41.7% agree and 20.6% strongly agree for being satisfied with their academic performance. According to this table, 2.8% of the students were strongly disagree, 6.7% disagree, 17.8% neutral, 37.8% agree and 35.0% strongly agree with their past results to encourage them to work hard. In this table 2.2% students were strongly disagree, 4.4% disagree, 13.9% neutral, 42.2% agree and 37.2% strongly agree regarding the dependency of academic performance on their efforts. This table showed that 5.6% students were strongly disagree, 11.1% disagree, 32.8% neutral, 30.0% agree and 20.6% strongly agree about spending most of their time in university with friends and teachers to discussing academic work/revising for examination. According to this table, 1.7% students were strongly disagree, 5.6% disagree, 22.8% neutral, 40.0% agree and 30.0% strongly agree for depending their academic performance on their skills to be organized. The above table showed that 4.4% strongly disagree, 11.7% disagree, 32.8% neutral, 32.2% agree and 18.9% strongly agree for being successful in finishing their entire homework task every day. According to this table, 3.3% students were strongly disagree, 3.9% disagree, 15.0% neutral, 46.7% agree and 31.1% strongly agree regarding the satisfaction of their parents with their grades/results. This table showed that 1.1% students were strongly disagree, 5.0% disagree, 14.4% neutral, 39.4% agree and 40.0% strongly agree for being successful always in exams. There are 2.8% students who strongly disagree, 1.7% disagree, 11.7% neutral, 38.3% agree and 45.6% strongly agree with their positive attitude being helpful in their exams.

Table 4: Correlation

Correlations	1	2	3
Spearman's rho	Institutional Environment	.317**	1.000
	Academic Performance	.490**	.503**
		.000	.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Spearman's rho correlation identifies that self-efficacy is significant related with institutional environment ($r = .317$, $p < 0.05$) and academic performance ($r = .490$, $p < 0.05$) where institutional environment and academic performance are strongly related ($r = .503$, $p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Chi square test (Institutional environment * Academic performance)

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1281.567 ^a	896	.000
Likelihood Ratio	504.181	896	1.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	52.141	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	180		

a. 957 cells (100.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is .01.

There is strong relationship between Institutional environment and Academic performance.

Table 6: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.651 ^a	.423	.417	.47124

a. Predictors: (Constant), institutional environment,

Model summary shows that the dependent variables and Independent variable have strong relationship. R Square value 0.417 shows that 41.7% of variance will be explained by institutional environment variables on academic performance.

VIII. DISCUSSION

The study found that more than one third (38.9%) of the respondents were agree that extra work/assignment given by teachers enhance understanding of the students whereas (20.6%) were neutral in this regard. The study also found that less than one half (45.0%) of the respondents were agree that teachers rewarded/encouraged them when they perform well in class. It was found that more than two fifths (43.9%) of the respondents were agree that they usually have sufficient internal exams. Regarding availability of class teachers, more than one third (36.7%) were agree that they had free access to consult their teachers for understanding concepts even after class. It was found more than one third (35.6%) of them confirmed that their teachers mark and return their assignments on time whereas less than one fourth (21.1%) were neutral. Role of institutional administration confirmed the findings of the studies of McGrath & Braunstein, (1997), Tross, Harper, Osher & Kneidinger (2000) and Braxton (2000) regarding availability of Head Teacher that more than one third (36.7%) of the respondents were agree that they had free access to Head Teacher for consultation in case of any problem which is always supportive to the students. Findings of the current study regarding role of teacher and Head Teacher within the premises of institutional environment strengthened the findings of the studies of Chukwuemeka (2013), Turner & Bowen (1999) and Wenglinsky (2001).

The present study also found that less than one third (30.0%) of the respondents were agree that they had sufficient time in university for preparation of the exams whereas less than one fourth (23.9%) of them were neutral in this regard. Further it was found that more than one third (38.3%) of the respondents found institutional environment helpful for study in their classrooms. For library and books it was found that less than one half (45.0%) of the respondents were agree that their university library has adequate with relevant books relating study/subject requirements for students. These findings are in line with the findings of Sunday (2012), Benware & Deci, (1984), Lizzio, Wilson & Simons (2002). It was found that little more than one third (33.3%) of the respondents were agree that students clearly understood and followed the motto, vision and mission of the university whereas less than one third (27.8%) were neutral in this regard. The present study found proved that institutional environment affects the academic performance of the students. The attention gaining response found in the section of institutional environment was that in all items of the section, highest response was on Agree which was point 4 out of 5 point scaling). The reason behind it would be the diplomatic/moderating attitude of the students so that their results might not be affected or something else.

The study found that less than one half (45.0%) of the respondents were agree regarding fulfillment of their academic goals and targets whereas 18.9% were neutral in this regard. It was found that 41.7% agree for being satisfied with their academic performance because 37.8% respondents responded that their past results encourage them to work hard whereas 15.6% were disagree because they were not satisfied with their academic performance. It

was also found that less than one half (42.2%) believe that their academic performance dependent on their efforts, 40.0% believe on their skills to be organized whereas 22.8% were neutral. When the respondents were asked about spending most of their time in university with friends and teachers to discussing academic work/revising for examination, little less than one third (32.8%) were responded neutral. It was found that less than one third (32.2%) respondents successfully finish their entire homework task every day. On the other hand, exact two fifth (40.0%) were strongly hopeful to be successful in exams. Because they (45.6%) strongly believe that positive attitude will be helpful in their exams. The study found that 46.7% were agreed regarding the satisfaction of their parents with their grades/results. Findings regarding academic performance of university students in higher learning are in line with different previous studies including the studies of Irfan et al., (2012) and Good (2009).

IX. CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the role and strategies of class teacher in terms of giving homework/assignment, conducting sufficient internal Exams and giving them rewards on performing well in the class enhanced their understanding in subjects/concepts. Consequently, students are fulfilling their academic goals and objectives, that makes them satisfied with their prevailing academic performance and this academic status of students encourages them to work hard for upgrading their goals in future too. It is also concluded that the students had free access to and availability of teacher and Head Teacher/ Head of Institution for consulting about their problems that makes the institutional environment conducive for students. It was found that the university had sufficient administrative & infrastructural facilities like library with adequate relevant books relating study/subject, park/playground, proper classrooms that was supportive for the students. Consequently, the students spent time within the premises of university preparing for readings (peer discussions about daily lectures, class tests/assignments and for exam preparations).

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